

Parental Involvement and Learners' Academic Performance

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15411698

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Abstract:

Parental involvement is one of the determinants of the academic success of learners. Parents' major obligation is to raise their children to become productive and responsible citizens. The key purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between parental involvement and the learners' academic performance of the 80 respondents in one of the elementary schools in a large-sized division in Central Visayas. Descriptive, quantitative research was conducted and used a 30-item survey questionnaire as a tool to gather data on the involvement of parents in children's education. The results revealed that the level of parental involvement in supervising child progress, communication and support, and school engagement was high. The level of learners' academic performance was fairly satisfactory. There was no significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the three areas when compared according to age, number of siblings, and grade level. Further, there was no significant relationship between the level of parental involvement and learners' academic performance. This calls for school authorities to design programs and activities that would increase parents' involvement in their children's school life.

Keywords: Parental Involvement, Academic Performance, Learners, Manjuyod, Negros Oriental

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Parental involvement is one of the most significant factors in the development of children. This is due to the authority and skill they have to shape and develop their children into motivated, inspired, and lenient people with their explicit involvement in the process of learning activities (Naite, 2021). Contrarily, parents without involvement in their children's education process are merely considered to demotivate and demoralize their children through negligence. This, in turn, has a negative effect on their performance. According to Young (2018), parental involvement comprises parenting attitudes, communication and support, and engagement in school activities of their children, inside or outside the school environment. Parents make the greatest difference to a child's achievement by supporting their learning at home and activities in school (Casey et al., 2018).

On the other hand, academic performance is defined as how well a student does in school. Learners' performance is important for producing high-quality graduates who will lead and work for the country for economic growth. However, during the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), the Philippines ranked bottom four among 64 countries (Dalauta et al., 2024). Thus, the country needs to deal with this bad performance, and one of the factors that could help increase the performance of the learners is parental involvement (Leander and Fabella, 2020).

In the present research venue, the researcher personally observed that during the administration of the Early Language, Literacy, and Numeracy Assessment (ELLNA), a great number of learners performed unsatisfactorily, particularly in key stage 1 learners (Grades 1-3). Many of the learners have poor literacy and numeracy skills, which affects their overall academic performance in school. One of the causes is parents' lack of involvement in their children's learning activities (Mangila, 2020). Most parents rely on and pass all the responsibilities to the teachers. Some of the parents did not get involved in school activities because they were struggling financially and had no resources to provide. Moreover, some parents have no time to communicate and support their children's learning activities because they prioritize earning a living to feed the family. With the facts cited, the researcher was motivated to conduct a study to assess the relationship between parental involvement and learners' academic performance to formulate intervention plans and activities to help improve the performance of the learners.

Current State of Knowledge

Parents serve as children's first educators and role models, playing a vital role in shaping their learning and academic success. Parental involvement—particularly through encouragement and meaningful feedback—significantly enhances a child's engagement and performance (Young, 2018). Supervision, as a core aspect of involvement,

influences children's behavior and adaptation in school, with parents uniquely positioned to support their children's needs across various environments (Ochoa & Torre, 2017). According to Flanagan et al. (2019), supervising child progress involves actively monitoring and guiding their activities, but this responsibility is often neglected due to parental absence or overcommitment to work. As a result, poor supervision stemming from limited time or awareness undermines effective parenting and child development.

Parental involvement, particularly through supervision and participation in school activities, significantly boosts children's motivation, confidence, and academic engagement. The presence of parents during school events serves as a morale booster, helping students build self-esteem and a positive attitude toward learning. Germudo (2021) found that parental involvement remains consistent regardless of profile variables like age, number of siblings, or grade level, as parents tend to be actively engaged in their children's education. Furthermore, communication and support from parents are more influential on academic success than socio-economic status or family background (Benner, Boyle, & Sadler, 2016), with the strongest impact seen when learning is supported both at home and in school (Casey et al., 2018). Open communication between parents and teachers is essential for fostering a strong home-school partnership, enhancing student outcomes. While Naite (2020) noted that factors such as age, education, employment, and marital status influence involvement, the overarching recommendation is for parents to be consistently present and supportive in their children's education.

Learning support is a crucial factor in child development, with children performing better academically when they have opportunities to learn and receive support from parents, teachers, and schools (Bartolome, 2017). A strong partnership between these parties leads to academic success, and when parents are involved, children feel valued and motivated to do their best. Parental involvement also provides a role model, inspiring children to actively engage in their education (Llego, 2022). Additionally, parental engagement in school activities positively impacts academic achievement, behavior, and social-emotional development. While there is no one-size-fits-all approach to involvement, it is essential for parents to find activities that suit their schedules and align with their interests, ensuring they can provide meaningful support to their child's education (Llego, 2022).

Most parents participate in the planning of classroom activities and engage in community and family social activities for their children in school. According to Sivertsen (2015), children benefit socially when their parents are engaged in extracurricular activities. Parent engagement strengthens the child's friendships. Parents can ensure that their child has a strong social network that is diverse and inclusive. Likewise, Wood & Bauman (2017) concluded that parent engagement has a positive impact on educational outcomes. Parents benefit when they are involved in a child's education. Parents are more informed about their child's educational growth and needs when they are involved.

Academic performance talks about how students are accomplishing their responsibilities and studies. According to Albarico et al. (2023), educational students are the most important asset. The students' academic performance plays a vital role in producing outstanding-quality individuals who will become leaders and the manpower of a particular country, consequently responsible for the country's social and economic development. Children's education is a joint undertaking of teachers and parents; both can provide a consistently structured environment for a conducive atmosphere of student learning. Parents should never rely on teachers alone for the development of their children; instead, they should take this as their full responsibility. Pinatil et al. (2022) found that the majority of the learners performed satisfactorily because their parents were relatively involved with their schooling. The more their parents are involved in their school life, the better their academic performance. Perocho (2023) found that the level of parental involvement significantly influenced the pupil's academic performance. Likewise, Tus (2021) resulted in a significant relationship between parental involvement and students' academic performance.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is grounded in the Theory of Parental Involvement by Epstein (1980) and the Theory of Academic Performance (ToP) by Elger (2007). Epstein's theory emphasizes the importance of school-family partnerships and outlines clear strategies for different types of parental involvement in education. It highlights the vital role parents play in coordinating with the school to ensure continuous engagement throughout a child's academic journey, fostering a stronger connection between children, parents, teachers, and the community. This theory underscores that parental involvement is crucial to students' academic success, particularly in literacy development, as parents' support and early communication with their children can significantly influence their academic outcomes.

Elger's Theory of Academic Performance (2007) focuses on the factors that contribute to academic success, such as knowledge, skills, identity, personal and fixed factors. Elger identifies three key elements for effective performance: a performer's mindset, immersion in a supportive environment, and engagement in reflective practice. Higher academic performance enhances not only academic quality but also a student's capabilities, motivation, and skills. By applying ToP to this study, it emphasizes the need to support students at all levels, setting challenging goals from the start of the school year, while viewing failure as part of the learning process that drives improved academic performance.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the level of parental involvement and the level of learners' academic performance in one of the elementary schools in a large division in Central Visayas during the first and second grading periods of the School Year 2023-2024. More specifically, it aimed to determine: 1) the level of parental involvement in terms of supervising a child's progress, communication and support, and school engagement; 2) level of learners' academic performance; 3) the significant difference on level of parental involvement when grouped and compared by age, number of siblings, and grade level; and 4) the relationship between the level of parental involvement and learners' academic performance.

Methodology

This section presents a discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedures for data analysis

Research Design

This study used a descriptive research design to assess the level of parental involvement and learners' academic performance at an elementary school in Central Visayas during the 1st and 2nd grading periods of the 2023-2024 school year. As De Belen (2015) suggests, a descriptive design is ideal for studies that explore current conditions, relationships, opinions, and behaviors. This approach was chosen to gather information on the characteristics of the study and to evaluate the nature of the relationship between parental involvement and academic performance, aiding in making professional judgments about these factors.

Study Respondents

The respondents of the study were 80 parents in one of the schools of Negros Oriental. The researcher used purposive sampling, as all respondents to the survey fit a particular profile for the study.

Instruments

This study employed a self-made questionnaire with 30 items on parental involvement in the areas of supervising child's progress, communications and support, and school engagement with 10 items per area. The respondents were asked to rate each item using a five-point Likert scale containing the following scores with range and description: 5 – always; 4 – often; 3 – sometimes; 2 - rarely; and 1 – almost never. The research instrument was subjected to reliability with the results of 0.944 which interpreted as "excellent" and a validity with the result of 4.56 which make the instrument "valid".

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent and from the school head of the subject school. Upon approval, the researcher properly coordinated with classroom grade advisers that elicit 100% confidence in the administration of the instrument. The researcher gave enough time for the respondent to reflect and to ensure more accurate and quality information. The questionnaires were gathered, recorded, and analyzed. The data gathered from the responses of the respondents was tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used in the computer processing of the encoded data.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme and weighted mean to determine the level of parental involvement in the areas of supervising a child's progress, communication and support, and school engagement.

Objective No. 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and weighted mean to determine the level of learners' academic performance.

Objective No. 3 used the comparative analytical scheme, Mann-Whitney U-test, and Kruskal Wallis H test as statistical tools to determine the significant difference in the level of parental involvement when grouped and compared according to profile variables.

Objective No. 4 used the relational analytical scheme and Spearman rho to determine the relationship between the level of parental involvement and learners' academic performance.

Ethical Consideration

To ensure no human rights are violated during the conduct of research, the researcher gave importance to the respondents' voluntary participation, informed consent, risk of harm, confidentiality, and anonymity. Participation in the study was voluntary, and the respondents could withdraw at any time without any consequences. They were informed about the academic purpose of the study. Confidentiality was ensured as only the researcher/s had access to the research data. Moreover, during the conduct of the study, the researcher strictly observed the governing guidelines and policies of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 to ensure security measures are in place to protect personal and sensitive information.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Parental Involvement in the Areas of Supervising Child's Progress, Communication and Support and School Engagement

The first objective was to determine the level of parental involvement in terms of supervising a child's progress, communication and support, and school engagement.

Table 1

Level of Parental Involvement According to Supervising Child Progress

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent, I...		
1. supervise my child's daily routine.	3.69	High Level
2. schedule the learning and play time of my children at home.	3.68	High Level
3. regularly monitor my child's performance in exams, quizzes, tests, and performance task activities.	3.58	High Level
4. establish limits and rules for my child's recreational activities.	3.64	High Level
5. am alert and responsive to my child's daily educational necessities.	3.70	High Level
6. make sure that my children complete their homework and assignments.	3.44	Moderate Level
7. monitor my child's daily activities at school such as class participation, attendance, food eaten, etc.	3.70	High Level
8. spend time assisting my children on their classroom projects and tasks.	4.15	High Level
9. see to it that my child follows the policies and regulations of the school.	3.90	High Level
10. ensure that my child goes to school early and goes home on time.	3.45	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.74	High Level

Table 1 presents the level of parental involvement in terms of supervising child progress with an overall mean score of 3.74, interpreted as a high level. This shows that most parents are supervising their child's learning progress. Investigating further, respondents assessed a highest mean score of 4.15 on item No. 8, stating to spend time assisting my children on their classroom projects and tasks" is interpreted as a high level. On the other hand, the lowest mean of 3.44 was on item No. 6 stating to make sure that my children complete their homework and assignments is interpreted as a moderate level. The results imply that parents occasionally supervise in completing the child's assignment and homework, while some of the parents were not aware whether their children did their assignments or not. This is because some parents are working during the day, so they don't have enough time to supervise their children's assignments and homework. Whereas some parents admitted that they seldom checked the assignments of their children and helped their children with their school projects because they were already tired and exhausted after doing household chores. Added to this is the misconception of some parents, who believe that it is not their primary responsibility to be involved with the children's schooling but that it is the teacher's responsibility to ensure that their children perform well in school. The result relates to that of Flanagan et al. (2019). The researchers opined that supervising child progress is the act of directing and watching over the performance and activities of the children in your care. Poor parental supervision can include low parental monitoring and low levels of parental knowledge about children's whereabouts and activities. This lack of parental supervision occurs because of the absence of parents in the home, either because they are not there physically or because they are too busy out of the home working on multiple jobs.

Table 2

Level of Parental Involvement According to Communication and Support

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent, I...		
1. talk with my children about their needs in school.	3.41	Moderate Level
2. regularly communicate with the teachers about the academic status of my children.	3.61	High Level
3. collaborate with my child's teachers on how to improve their performance.	3.56	High Level
4. talk with my children about their problems and difficulties in school.	4.03	High Level
5. share with my children my interests and likes that could help improve their academic performance.	3.70	High Level
6. financially support my children's school activities.	3.54	High Level
7. support whenever my child joins in academic competitions and contests.	3.56	High Level
8. talk with my child about his/her academic performance in school.	4.00	High Level
9. provide my child with appropriate learning materials to improve his/her performance.	3.88	High Level
10. support my child's learning by providing nutritious meals and adequate sleep time.	3.54	High Level
Overall Mean	3.68	High Level

Table 2 discloses the results on the level of parental involvement in terms of communication and support with an overall mean score of 3.68, interpreted as a high level. This shows that most parents actively support their child's school activities. Analyzing further, the respondents obtained the highest mean score of 4.03 on item No. 4 stating to talk with my children about their problems and difficulties in school is interpreted as a high level, while the lowest mean of 3.41 was on item No. 1, stating to talk with my children about their needs in school is interpreted as a moderate level.

The result implies that some parents rarely talk to their children about their needs in school unless their children call their attention to the school materials needed. This is because some parents don't have enough financial resources because they prioritize the basic needs of the family. A balance of education at home and school molds a student's actual learning. Hence, parents must see to it that children are provided with their basic needs as well as their educational needs. The result aligns with that of Bartolome (2017). Learning support has been found to be an important variable in child development. Children perform better in school when they have opportunities to learn. When parents, teachers, and schools support one another and build a strong partnership, it will result in academic success. In addition, when parents are supportive and involved, the child feels a sense of importance and value. This encourages the child to work hard and do their best. Parental involvement also provides the child with a role model to follow. Seeing their parents actively involved in their education can inspire the child to do the same (Llego, 2022).

Table 3

Level of Parental Involvement According to School Engagement

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a parent, I...		
1. participate in my child's various school activities.	3.35	Moderate Level
2. participate in the planning of classroom activities with the teacher.	3.89	High Level
3. volunteer for a specific role in the school activities.	3.46	Moderate Level
4. regular attendance at PTA meetings and conferences.	3.55	High Level
5. encourage other parents to participate in school-related activities and projects.	3.99	High Level
6. assist teachers during my child's field trips, camping, and recollection.	3.26	Moderate Level
7. support PTA activities and projects that promote learners' performance.	3.73	High Level
8. assist teachers in an information campaign of the school's various activities.	3.56	High Level
9. participate in fundraising activities for my child's school activities and projects.	3.56	High Level
10. participate in community and family social activities at my child's school.	4.00	High Level
Overall Mean	3.74	High Level

Table 3 divulges the data on the level of parental involvement in terms of school engagement with an overall mean score of 3.74, interpreted as a high level. This entails that most parents actively engage in their child’s school activities and projects. Examining further, the respondents perceived a highest mean score of 4.00 on item No. 10 starting to participate in community and family social activities at my child’s school is interpreted as a high level, while the lowest mean of 3.90 was on item No. 6 starting to assist teachers during my child’s field trips, camping, and recollection is interpreted as a moderate level. The result implies that parents seldom assisted teachers in school activities and seldom allowed their children to join in field trips or educational tours. The reason is that most parents are just average wage earners and don’t have enough financial resources to allow their children to join in field trips as they prioritize the basic needs of the family. Learners are motivated to study when they see their parents participate and allow their children to join field trips. This enhances a strong collaborative relationship between the school and the parents to improve the learning capabilities of the learners and their academic achievement. With their parents involved in their education, children tend to focus more on schoolwork. The finding relates to that of Llego (2022). Engagement of parents in school activities is another influencing factor on learners’ academic achievement in literacy. It is suggested that when the school cultivates parental engagement, the students stand to benefit a great deal, leading to results such as increased academic achievement, better behavior in the classroom, and a positive change in the child’s personality. In addition, when parents are involved in their children’s education, children are more likely to do well in school and have better social and emotional development. The best way for parents to get involved in their children’s education is to find an activity that they are interested in that fits their schedule. There is no one-size-fits-all approach to parental involvement; what works for one family may not work for another. The most important thing is that parents find an activity they are comfortable with and feel benefits for their child.

Learners’ Academic Performance

The second objective was to determine the level of learners’ academic performance during the first and second grading period.

Table 4

Level of Learners’ Academic Performance During the First and Second Grading Period

Variable	Mean	Interpretation
Level of Learners’ Academic Performance	78.64	Fairly Satisfactory

Table 4 shows the learners’ academic performance during the first and second periods. The mean grade of the learners is 78.64. The result indicates that the learners showed fairly satisfactory performance in the first and second periods of the school year. Meaning the learners' performance was fair and needs improvement. With this rating, the parents must visit and follow up on their children’s performance and establish partnerships with the teacher that would help enhance their children’s performance in school. Because children’s education is a joint undertaking of teachers and parents, both can provide a consistently structured environment for a conducive atmosphere of student learning. Parents should never rely on teachers alone for the development of their children; instead, they should take this as their full responsibility. This relates to that of Pinatil et al. (2022), wherein the majority of the learners performed satisfactorily. The learners perceived that their parents were relatively involved with their schooling. The more their parents are involved in their school life, the better their academic performance.

Comparative Analysis Between the Level of Parental Involvement When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

The third objective was to determine the significant difference in the level of parental involvement in the areas of supervising child’s progress, communication and support, and school engagement when grouped and compared according to variables.

Table 5

Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement According to Supervising Child Progress When Grouped According to Age, Number of Siblings and Grade Level

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
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Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	37	42.04	738.50	0.581	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	43	39.17				
Number of Siblings	Few	26	46.33	550.50	0.119	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	54	37.69				
Grade Level	Grade 1	27	41.20	0.042	0.979	0.05	Not Significant
	Grade 2	18	39.83				
	Grade 3	35	40.30				

Table 5 summarizes the comparative analysis of the level of parental involvement in terms of supervising child progress according to profile variables. The computed p-values of variable age, number of siblings, and grade level are 0.581, 0.119, and 0.979, respectively, which are greater than 0.05 level of significance indicating no significant difference. The result implies that the level of parental involvement in terms of supervising child progress when grouped compared to age, number of siblings, and grade level does not vary. This is because most parents find ways to spend time with their children's education regardless of their busy work schedules and household chores. Age, number of siblings, and grade level have nothing to do with parents' involvement in their children's education; they were anxiously involved in every facet of it. Parenting activities such as supervising their children's progress in school can motivate children to participate in school learning activities. The more involved the parents are in school activities, the more confident the learners become, hence the more motivated they are in learning. The presence of their parents in school during activities would serve as a morale booster for the students and eventually build their self-confidence. The results are supported by the study conducted by Germudo (2021), wherein she found that there was no significant difference in the level of parental involvement when grouped and compared according to profile variables.

Table 6

Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement According to Communication and Support When Grouped According to Age, Number of Siblings and Grade Level

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	37	42.00	740.00	0.591	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	43	39.21				
Number of Siblings	Few	26	43.75	617.50	0.384	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	54	38.94				
Grade Level	Grade 1	27	39.93	0.074	0.963	0.05	Not Significant
	Grade 2	18	41.78				
	Grade 3	35	40.29				

Table 6 presents the comparative analysis of the level of parental involvement in terms of communication and support according to profile variables. The computed p-values of variable age, number of siblings, and grade level are 0.591, 0.384, and 0.963, respectively, which are greater than 0.05 level of significance indicating no significant difference. The result implies that the level of parental involvement in terms of communication and support, when compared to age, number of siblings, and grade level, does not differ. This is because, regardless of parents' backgrounds, they prioritize communicating and supporting their child's school activities. Communication is seen as the basic foundation for learning and the means for developing parent involvement programs and building a strong home-school

partnership. When parents are involved, the learners feel that they are supported, and they react more positively, which is evident in their academic achievement.

However, the result contradicts that of Naite (2020), wherein age, educational level, employment, and marital status of the parents had a greater impact on parental involvement. The researcher suggested that parents should become more aware of the importance of visiting and supporting their children in school. In addition, in the study of Benner, Boyle, and Sadler (2016), Parents' communication and support for their children's learning influence performance irrespective of their family background variables such as social class, family size, and level of parental education.

Table 7

Difference in the Level of Parental Involvement According to School Engagement When Grouped According to Age, Number of Siblings and Grade Level

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	37	42.93	705.50	0.383	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	43	38.41				
Number of Siblings	Few	26	43.02	636.50	0.499	0.05	Not Significant
	Many	54	39.29				

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Kruskal Wallis H	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Grade Level	Grade 1	27	40.94	0.017	0.991	0.05	Not Significant
	Grade 2	18	40.06				
	Grade 3	35	40.39				

Table 7 shows the comparative analysis of the level of parental involvement in terms of school engagement according to profile variables. The computed p-values of variable age, number of siblings, and grade level are 0.383, 0.499, and 0.991, respectively, which are greater than 0.05 level of significance indicating no significant difference. The finding implies that the level of parental involvement in terms of school engagement does not vary when compared according to age, number of siblings, and grade level. This is because most parents actively engage in their children's school activities, regardless of their profile background. Most parents participate in the planning of classroom activities and engage in community and family social activities for their children in school. The result relates to that of Sivertsen (2015). Children benefit socially when their parents are engaged in extracurricular activities. Parent engagement strengthens the child's friendships. Parents can ensure that their child has a strong social network that is diverse and inclusive. Likewise, Wood & Bauman (2017) concluded that parent engagement has a positive impact on educational outcomes. Parents benefit when they are involved in a child's education. Parents are more informed about their child's educational growth and needs when they are involved.

Relational Analysis Between the Level of Parental Involvement and Learners' Academic Performance During the First and Second Grading Period

The fourth objective is to determine the relationship between the level of parental involvement and learners' academic performance.

Table 8

Relationship Between the Level of Parental Involvement Between the Level of Parental Involvement and Learners' Academic Performance During the First and Second Grading Period

Correlates	N	rho	Level of Sig	p-value	Interpretation
Level of Parental Involvement	80	-	0.05	0.312	Not Significant
	80	0.115			

Learners' Academic Performance

Table 8 discloses the relationship between the level of parental involvement and learners' academic performance. As manifested in Table 8, the computed p-value is 0.312, which is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This indicates the acceptance of the null hypothesis, suggesting that there is no significant relationship between the involvement of parents and the academic performance of the learners. It means that whether the parents involve or do not participate in their children's school learning activities, it will not affect the academic performance of the learners. The result contradicts that of Perocho (2023), wherein the level of parental involvement significantly influenced the pupil's academic performance. Likewise, Tus (2021) resulted in a significant relationship between parental involvement and students' academic performance.

Conclusions

Overall, the level of parental involvement was high concluding the majority if the of the parents are involved in their child's learning activities, particularly in the supervision, communication and supports and engagement school activities. However, there are still parents who are ignorant of their responsibilities particularly in monitoring and assisting their child's learning activities at home and in schools. Demographic backgrounds of the parents did not impede their ability to involve in their child's learning activities in school and at home. The result of this study serves as a guide for parents and teachers in finding ways to improve the academic performance of the learners. This calls for school authorities to design programs and activities that would increase parents' involvement in their children's school life.

Acknowledgment

This endeavor would not have been possible without the collective effort and support of many individuals. The researcher is deeply grateful for the guidance, motivation, and knowledge provided by the thesis adviser, as well as the sincere encouragement from academic leaders and the invaluable insights and support from the panel members throughout the process. Appreciation is also extended to colleagues and friends for their unwavering reinforcement and encouragement. Special thanks go to the parents who generously gave their time and honest responses in completing the research instrument. Above all, heartfelt gratitude is offered to the Divine Providence, whose blessings made the completion of this work possible.

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